

Teachers' Digital Literacy Skills and Implementation of Competency Based Curriculum in Junior Schools in Westlands Sub County, Kenya

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ABSTRACT: The study explored the impact of teachers' digital literacy skills on the implementation of the Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC) in Junior Schools in Westlands Sub-County, Nairobi, Kenya. The hypothesis tested was H01: There is no significant relationship between teachers' digital literacy skills and CBC implementation. The study was based on the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework, which integrates technology with teaching. A descriptive survey research design was used to describe the characteristics of teachers and schools. The target population included 127 public Junior Schools, 304 teachers, and 4 educational officers. Stratified sampling was applied to select 25 schools and 25 principals, while census sampling was used for the officers. Simple random sampling selected 61 teachers. Data was collected using interviews and questionnaires. Interview schedule were applied on Head teachers and CSOs and questionnaires for teachers were used as instruments for data collection. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, while qualitative data were processed through content analysis. The findings revealed a significant relationship between teachers' digital literacy skills and CBC implementation, with a Chi-square result of $\chi^2 = 32.050$ and $p = 0.000$ at the 0.05 significance level. The study concluded that teachers' digital literacy skills positively influence CBC implementation in public schools. The study recommended Teachers Service Commission to prioritize professional development programs to enhance digital literacy skills on using digital resources and platforms that align with the objectives of the CBC. Moreover, school heads be trained to foster environments that support the use of digital tools in CBC.

KEYWORDS: Influence, Implementation of Competency Based Curriculum, Teachers' digital literacy skills, Junior schools

1. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

The implementation of the Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC) in Kenya has brought about a transformative approach to education, emphasizing the development of critical thinking, creativity, and practical skills among learners. In the USA, Harris and Hofer (2019) explored the relationship between teachers' digital literacy skills and the implementation of competency-based education and found that higher digital literacy among educators positively influenced their ability to adopt innovative teaching strategies aligned with competency-based frameworks, enhancing student learning outcomes.

Wang and Liao (2023) examined the impact of professional development programs on teachers' digital literacy and their ability to implement competency-based education (CBE) in junior schools across the USA. Their study highlights an important link between ongoing teacher training and effective application of digital tools in classrooms. Teachers who participated in continuous digital skills training were more successful in adopting competency-based approaches, which emphasize personalized learning and the mastery of specific skills. This finding is essential for understanding how professional development plays a crucial role in transforming teaching practices.

Bates and Sangra (2020) focused on the role of teacher training in enhancing digital literacy in the UK, specifically in relation to implementing competency-based curricula. Their findings underscore the importance of targeted professional development in helping teachers build confidence in using digital tools. As the UK moves toward more competency-based curricula, equipping teachers with the necessary digital skills is essential to ensure that they can effectively integrate technology into their instructional strategies. Teacher training programs tailored to improving digital literacy can serve as a catalyst for more effective implementation of CBC in schools, which still grapple with disparities in access to educational technology.

In China, Wang, Yang, and Chen (2021) explored the relationship between teachers' digital literacy and their ability to implement innovative educational practices, including competency-based approaches. Their research found that teachers with advanced digital skills were more effective in utilizing technology, which in turn enhanced the implementation of new curricula. This

highlights the transformative role of digital literacy in enabling teachers to deliver personalized, competency-based education. Training teachers to become proficient in digital tools is crucial in a country that aims to modernize education systems through technology.

Adedoyin and Soykan (2024) specifically focus on Nigerian educators and the integration of digital tools in teaching practices while implementing the competency-based curriculum. They found that teachers who possessed robust digital literacy skills were more adept at leveraging technology to create interactive, collaborative, and student-centered learning environments. This is particularly important in Nigeria, where the introduction of CBC requires teachers to move away from traditional rote learning approaches toward methods that promote critical thinking, problem-solving, and personalized learning. Ezeani and Nwogwugwu (2021) further support the argument on digital literacy in Nigeria by examining the role of ICT in the classroom. Their research emphasized that teachers with higher levels of digital literacy were better equipped to integrate Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools into their daily teaching activities. This aligns with the findings of Ogunyemi and Adebayo (2020), reinforcing the idea that digital literacy is a key factor in achieving the goals of competency-based education. Ezeani and Nwogwugwu's study highlights that when teachers effectively utilize digital tools, they can enhance the learning process, enabling students to develop critical 21st-century skills. The integration of ICT in Nigerian classrooms, particularly in remote areas, is a pivotal step toward improving educational outcomes, and digital literacy programs for teachers are crucial for facilitating this integration.

Owusu-Acheaw and Osei-Kofi (2022) investigated the role of professional development in enhancing teachers' digital literacy skills for the effective implementation of the competency-based curriculum in Ghana and found that continuous training significantly improved teachers' confidence and ability to integrate digital resources into their teaching. Elbanna and Hamada (2023) examined the influence of teachers' digital literacy on the effectiveness of the competency-based curriculum in Egyptian junior schools and highlighted that teachers with higher levels of digital literacy were more successful in employing innovative teaching methods that aligned with the principles of the CBC, leading to better student learning outcomes.

In Tanzania, Mhando and Kihwele (2020) examined the impact of teachers' digital literacy skills on the implementation of the Competency-Based Curriculum in Tanzanian junior secondary schools and revealed that teachers with higher digital literacy levels were more effective in integrating technology into their teaching practices, which enhanced student engagement and learning outcomes. Mugisha and Sempewo (2023) examined the correlation between teachers' digital literacy and their teaching practices in Tanzanian schools implementing the Competency-Based Curriculum and highlighted that teachers who were digitally literate could create more interactive and student-centered learning environments.

In Uganda, Okwakol and Okurut (2021) explored how teachers' digital literacy skills influenced the implementation of the Competency-Based Curriculum and indicated that teachers with proficient digital skills were better equipped to adapt their teaching methods to meet the demands of the CBC, resulting in improved educational quality. Atuma and Kigozi (2024) studied the barriers to achieving digital literacy among teachers in Uganda and their impact on the implementation of the Competency-Based Curriculum and revealed that inadequate training and resources hindered teachers' ability to effectively utilize digital tools in their teaching.

In Rwanda, Niyigana and Umutooni (2022) investigated the influence of professional development programs on teachers' digital literacy skills and the subsequent implementation of the Competency-Based Curriculum in Rwandan junior schools and found that ongoing training significantly enhanced teachers' digital competencies, enabling them to effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices.

In Kenya, Imonje (2020) discusses the importance of digital literacy within the Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC), emphasizing that it extends beyond basic computer skills to include critical thinking, problem-solving, and responsible digital citizenship. She argues that technology integration is essential in fostering competencies that prepare students for future careers, advocating for the inclusion of ethical online practices and safe digital behavior. Imonje also highlights the need for equitable access to digital resources and ongoing teacher training to effectively implement digital literacy in the CBC framework, ensuring that all students, regardless of their socio-economic background, can benefit. Furthermore, Chepkonga (2015) emphasizes integration of ICT to promote effective management of secondary schools and it is important to enhance and provide principals with adequate training in various management systems for financial, administrative, human resource management, library and student personnel. Therefore the issue of training should be addressed for the benefits of ICT to be realized. According to Kireia,

P.G., Imonje, R.& Chepkonga, S. (2025), Head teachers should play a critical role in ensuring integration of digital skills in assessment procedures that align with the 21st century by providing teachers with the necessary support, digital resources and feedback to enhance their practice. Nderitu and Mwangi (2021) examined the relationship between teachers' digital literacy skills and the effective implementation of the Competency-Based Curriculum in public primary schools in Kenya and found that teachers with higher digital literacy were more capable of integrating technology into their teaching, which positively impacted student engagement and learning outcomes. Ochieng and Muli (2022) explored the impact of teachers' digital competence on the delivery of the Competency-Based Curriculum in secondary schools in Kenya and indicated that teachers who possessed strong digital skills were able to adopt innovative teaching methods, thereby enhancing the quality of education. Achieng and Anyango (2024) focused on the effects of professional development training on teachers' digital literacy and its subsequent impact on the implementation of the Competency-Based Curriculum in junior schools and discovered that targeted training programs significantly enhanced teachers' digital skills, leading to more effective curriculum delivery.

In Westlands Subcounty, Muthoni and Wanjiru (2021) investigated the impact of teachers' digital literacy skills on the implementation of the Competency-Based Curriculum in selected junior secondary schools in Nairobi and revealed that teachers with higher digital literacy levels were more effective in integrating technology into their teaching practices, which significantly enhanced student learning experiences. Ochieng and Ngoya (2022) conducted a study assessing teachers' preparedness and digital literacy skills in Westlands Sub County, focusing on their impact on the implementation of the CBC and found a strong correlation between teachers' digital skills and their ability to effectively deliver the curriculum, leading to improved student outcomes.

Statement of the problem

The implementation of the Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC) in Kenya has brought about a transformative approach to education, emphasizing the development of critical thinking, creativity, and practical skills among learners. The Ministry of Education has established policies aimed at integrating technology into teaching practices and has facilitated workshops and training programs to improve teachers' digital competencies. KICD has developed resources and guidelines that promote the use of digital tools in the delivery of the CBC, while TSC has incorporated digital literacy requirements into the professional development frameworks for teachers. However, the successful execution of this curriculum heavily relies on teachers' digital literacy skills. Despite these initiatives, there remains a significant gap in understanding how teachers' digital literacy skills directly influence the implementation of the CBC in junior schools. In Westlands Sub County, Nairobi City County, there is a pressing need to examine the influence of teachers' digital literacy on the successful implementation of the CBC, as challenges in this area may undermine the intended outcomes of the curriculum since many educators still face challenges in adapting to new technologies, which may hinder their ability to deliver the curriculum effectively. This study therefore seeks to investigate influence of teachers' digital literacy skills on the implementation of competency based curriculum in junior schools in Westlands Sub County, Nairobi City County, Kenya.

Objective of the Study

The objective of the study was to determine the influence of teachers' digital literacy skills on the implementation of competency based curriculum in junior schools in Westlands Sub County, Nairobi City County, Kenya.

Research Hypothesis

The study was based on the research hypothesis H₀₁: There is no Significant relationship between teachers' digital literacy skills and implementation of Competency Based Curriculum in Junior Schools in Westlands Sub County Nairobi City County, Kenya.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Contextualization of the research problem

Nambiro (2020) investigated the relationship between teacher preparedness and the successful implementation of the Competency-Based Curriculum in junior schools in Kenya and found that inadequate training and lack of resources were significant barriers that hindered effective implementation. Omondi (2021) explored the challenges faced by teachers in implementing the CBC in selected junior schools in Kenya and identified issues such as insufficient training, limited access to educational resources, and resistance to change as major impediments to effective curriculum delivery. Okwiri and Mutai (2022)

examined the influence of resource availability on the implementation of the CBC in junior schools and revealed that schools with better access to teaching materials and technology were more successful in executing the curriculum effectively. Karanja and Njuguna (2023) highlighted the importance of continuous professional development in enhancing teachers' skills for the implementation of the CBC and concluded that regular training sessions significantly improved teachers' confidence and competence in delivering the new curriculum. Mwangi et al. (2024) analyzed the effectiveness of the Competency-Based Curriculum on student learning outcomes in junior schools and indicated that the CBC positively impacted student engagement and achievement, although it emphasized the need for better teacher training to maximize its benefits.

Omondi (2021) investigated the relationship between teachers' digital literacy skills and the effective implementation of the CBC in junior schools in Kenya and found that teachers with higher digital literacy were better equipped to utilize technology in their teaching, which positively influenced the curriculum delivery. Nyaboga and Muli (2022) examined how teachers' digital competence affects their teaching methods within the framework of the CBC and revealed that teachers who were proficient in digital tools were more likely to adopt innovative teaching strategies that align with the principles of the CBC. Karanja et al. (2023) explored the role of teachers' digital literacy in enhancing student engagement and participation in learning activities within the CBC framework and highlighted that teachers who effectively integrated digital tools into their teaching significantly increased student interest and involvement. Achieng' and Okoth (2024) analyzed the challenges faced by teachers in developing digital literacy skills necessary for the implementation of the CBC and identified gaps in training, infrastructure, and support systems as significant barriers to enhancing digital skills among educators. Muriuki and Were (2024) investigated the impact of professional development programs on teachers' digital literacy and their ability to implement the CBC and suggested that targeted training significantly improved teachers' digital skills, leading to more effective curriculum implementation.

Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework developed by Punya Mishra and Matthew J. Koehler in 2006 which integrates three core components of effective teaching with technology: Content Knowledge (CK), Pedagogical Knowledge (PK), and Technological Knowledge (TK). The TPACK framework posits that effective teaching requires an understanding of how to integrate technology (TK) with pedagogical methods (PK) and subject content (CK) to enhance student learning. The Content Knowledge (CK) refers to the teacher's understanding of the subject matter they are teaching. For the Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC), teachers need a deep knowledge of the curriculum content. The Pedagogical Knowledge (PK) encompasses the methods and strategies teachers use to deliver content effectively and how its crucial for teachers to adopt pedagogical approaches that align with the principles of the CBC. Technological Knowledge (TK) involves the understanding and ability to use various digital tools and technologies. In the context of the CBC, teachers' digital literacy skills are essential for effectively integrating technology into their teaching practices. The TPACK framework is particularly relevant for this study as it provides a structure for examining the influence of teachers' digital literacy skills on the implementation of the Competency-Based Curriculum in junior schools in Westlands Sub County, Nairobi City County, Kenya. The study aims to explore how teachers' ability to use technology (TK) enhances their pedagogical practices (PK) and effectively conveys the curriculum content (CK).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey research design was used as it allows the researcher to describe characteristics of an individual or group as they really are (Shikokoti, Okoth and Abungana, 2024). Descriptive survey is only concerned with conditions or relationships that exist, opinions that are held and process that are ongoing. The target population for the study was 127 public Junior Schools in the Westlands Sub-County, 304 Junior school teachers, 2 Sub County Quality Assurance and Standards Officers and 2 Curriculum Support Officers. In order to select the lecturers, a 20% sample was used which was deemed to be a big sample (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2019) and large enough to identify a significant effect (Kothari, 2019). Stratified sampling on 25 schools and on 25 principals, census sampling 2 QASO and 2 CSOs and simple random sampling on 61 teachers. According to Cohen, Manions & Morrison (2018), simple random sampling technique allows a researcher to get a representative sample without biasness. Therefore, all teachers had equal chances to participate. Interview schedule for Head teachers and CSOs and questionnaires for teachers were used as instruments for data collection. To enhance the content validity of the instruments a pre-test of the instruments was carried out. Piloting aimed at testing the clarity of test items, suitability of language used and the feasibility of the

study. The reliability of the instruments was determined using test-retest technique. Pearson product moment correlation was used to compute the reliability coefficient (Shikokoti, Okoth and Abungana, 2024). Descriptive statistics were used in the analyses of the collected data. For inferential statistic, Chi-square test for hypothesis one was used to test the relationship between the hypothesis. The Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS), version 22, was used to code and enter the data into the computer for analysis after the questions were reviewed for completeness.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Table 1: Teachers’ responses on there is Availability of computers in the school

Statement	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std
Little Extent	36	60.0	2.93	1.191
Large Extent	16	26.7		
Very Large Extent	18	18.3		
Total	32	100.0		

Table 1 shows that majority, a total of 36 teachers, accounting for 60.0% of the participants, reported that there is Availability of computers in the school to a Little Extent while 18 teachers (13.3%) stated there is Availability of computers in the school to a Very Large Extent. The mean score for this question was 2.93, with a standard deviation of 1.191. This implies that few computers are available. The findings are in Line with Wambui and Kirui (2020) explored the availability of ICT resources, including computers, in Kenyan schools and how teachers' digital literacy impacted the implementation of CBC and found that while urban schools were better equipped with computers, rural areas still faced significant deficits.

Table 2 shows Lecturers responses on lecturers have access to research facilities and resources

Table 2: Teachers’ responses on I have Have been trained to use ICT in CBC

Statement	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std
Large Extent	42	70.0	4.30	1.197
Very Large Extent	18	30.0		
Total	60	100.0		

Table 2 shows a total of 42 teachers, accounting for 70.0% of the participants, reported that they have Have been trained to use ICT in CBC to a Large Extent while 18 teachers (30.0%) stated they have Have been trained to use ICT in CBC to a Very Large Extent. The mean score for this question was 4.30, with a standard deviation of 1.197. This implies that teachers have been trained to use ICT in CBC. The findings are consistent with Kiptalam and Koskei (2019) examined the effectiveness of ICT training programs for teachers and how these impacted their ability to integrate digital tools into CBC. The study found that teachers who received formal ICT training, especially through government initiatives such as the Digital Literacy Programme (DLP), were more confident in using technology for classroom instruction demonstrated an enhanced ability to prepare digital learning materials, manage online resources, and facilitate student-centered learning, which is essential for CBC implementation. Table 3 shows Teachers’ response on How often are the computers used for teaching

Table 3: Teachers’ response on How often are the computers used for teaching

Statement	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std
Little Extent	12	20.0	3.83	1.011
Large Extent	34	56.7		
Very Large Extent	14	23.3		
Total	60	100.0		

Table 3 shows on How often are the computers used for teaching Majority, A total of 34 teachers, accounting for (56.7%) of the participants, reported that they have How often are the computers used for teaching to a Large Extent while 14 teachers (23.3%)

stated How often are the computers used for teaching to a Very Large Extent. The mean score for this question was 3.83, with a standard deviation of 1.011. This implies that teachers use computers frequently. The findings Concur with Ndungu and Gichuhi (2020) who analyzed how often computers were used in classrooms based on teachers' ICT proficiency and found that in schools where teachers possessed strong digital literacy skills, computers were frequently used as part of the teaching process in lesson planning, assessments, and interactive learning sessions multiple times a week, facilitating a more student-centered approach aligned with CBC. Table 4 shows Teachers' response on there is Alignment of technology with stated objectives

Table 4: Teachers' response on there is Alignment of technology with stated objectives

Statement	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std
Little Extent	11	20.0	3.60	1.045
Some Extent	16	26.7		
Large Extent	19	31.7		
Very Large Extent	14	23.3		
Total	60	100.0		

Table 4 shows that majority, a total of 19 teachers, accounting for 31.7% of the participants, reported that there is Alignment of technology with stated objectives to a Large Extent while 16 teachers (26.7%) stated there is Alignment of technology with stated objectives to Some Extent and 14 teachers (23.3%) to a Very Large Extent respectively. The mean score for this question was 3.60, with a standard deviation of 1.045. This implies that the teachers align technology with the stated objectives. The findings are in Line Achieng and Mwangi (2019) who examined how well teachers with varying levels of digital literacy could align technology use with educational objectives in CBC and found that teachers with higher digital literacy skills were better able to integrate technology to achieve specific learning outcomes using tools such as educational software and online resources, to facilitate competency-based learning, ensuring that the use of technology directly supported the stated curriculum objectives. Table 5 shows Teachers' response on Effectiveness of ICT in teaching

Table 5: Teachers' response on Effectiveness of ICT in teaching

Statement	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std
Little Extent	20	33.3	3.92	0.926
Some Extent	22	36.7		
Very Large Extent	18	30.0		
Total	60	100.0		

Table 5, shows a total of 22 teachers, accounting for 36.7% of the participants, reported that they have Effectiveness of ICT in teaching to Some Extent while 20 teachers (33.3%) stated they have Effectiveness of ICT in teaching to a Little Extent. The mean score for this question was 3.27, with a standard deviation of 1.219. This implies that the teachers are effective in teaching ICT. The findings are consistent with Kariuki and Ndung'u (2020) who investigated the effectiveness of ICT tools in enhancing teaching and learning outcomes under CBC and revealed that teachers with advanced digital literacy skills were able to effectively integrate ICT into their lesson delivery, resulting in improved student engagement, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills by utilizing various digital platforms to create interactive learning environments, aligning well with the CBC's learner-centered approach. Table 6 shows Teachers' response on How often do you use internet for searching educational content

Table 6: Teachers' response on How often do you use internet for searching educational content

Statement	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std
Little Extent	2	3.3	4.02	1.033
Some Extent	22	36.7		
Large Extent	15	25.0		
Very Large Extent	21	35.0		
Total	60	100.0		

Table 6 shows on How often do you use internet for searching educational content, Majority, A total of 22 teachers, accounting for (36.7%) of the participants, reported that they have How often do you use internet for searching educational content to Some Extent while 21 teachers (35.0%) stated How often do you use internet for searching educational content to a Very Large Extent and 15 teachers (25.0%) to a Large Extent. The mean score for this question was 3.92, with a standard deviation of 0.926. This implies that teachers use the internet for searching educational content. The findings concur with Otieno and Mwema (2020) who investigated how often teachers used the internet to search for educational content in CBC implementation and found that teachers with advanced digital literacy skills frequently used the internet, often daily, to find resources that supplemented CBC instruction leveraging on online platforms for accessing lesson plans, instructional videos, and interactive content, which they integrated into their classroom practices to enhance learning outcomes.

Table 7 shows Teachers’ response on Setting up ICT devices for learning

Table 7: Teachers’ response on Setting up ICT devices for learning

Statement	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std
Little Extent	3	5.0	4.02	1.033
Some Extent	22	36.7		
Large Extent	6	10.0		
Very Large Extent	29	48.3		
Total	60	100.0		

Table 7 shows a total of 29 teachers, accounting for 48.3% of the participants, reported that they have Effectiveness of ICT in teaching to a Very Large Extent while 20 teachers (36.7%) stated they have Effectiveness of ICT in teaching to Some Extent. The mean score for this question was 3.27, with a standard deviation of 1.219. This implies that the teachers are effective in teaching ICT. The findings are consistent with Kariuki and Ndung’u (2020) who investigated the effectiveness of ICT tools in enhancing teaching and learning outcomes under CBC and revealed that teachers with advanced digital literacy skills were able to effectively integrate ICT into their lesson delivery, resulting in improved student engagement, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills by utilizing various digital platforms to create interactive learning environments, aligning well with the CBC’s learner-centered approach.

The researcher further used inferential statistics Chi-square test to analyse Objective test. To test objective one Chi-square test was done to determine the relationship between Teachers’ digital literacy skills (M=3.85, SD=0.984) and Competency Based Curriculum (M=4.24, SD=0.499)

Table 8 shows the Chi-square test between Teachers’ digital literacy skills and Competency Based Curriculum

Table 8: Chi Square test between Teachers’ digital literacy skills and Competency Based Curriculum

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	32.050 ^a	1	.000
Likelihood Ratio	32.752	1	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	7.847	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	60		

a. 5 cells (33.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.87.

The Chi-square result in Table 8 confirms that there is a relationship between Teachers digital literacy skills and Competency Based Curriculum. Objective 2 was tested using Chi square (df=1, Pearson Chi square(χ^2) =32.050 and p=0.000 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows there is a relationship between Teachers digital literacy skills and Competency Based Curriculum. This means that Teachers digital literacy skills has a great influence on Competency Based Curriculum. These findings are in line with research by Gathara and Wanjiru (2019) focused on the impact of teachers' digital literacy skills on the implementation of CBC in Kenyan schools

and revealed that teachers with high digital literacy were more effective in integrating technology into the CBC framework since they use various digital tools and platforms to support personalized learning, engage students in interactive activities, and align their teaching methods with the competency-based objectives hence digital literacy significantly enhanced the effectiveness of CBC by allowing teachers to create more engaging and flexible learning environments. In contrast, research by Mutai and Kiprotich (2021) examined schools where teachers had limited digital literacy and found that these teachers struggled with the integration of ICT in the classroom, often resorting to traditional teaching methods because lack of digital skills hindered the full implementation of CBC, as the curriculum relies heavily on technology to facilitate student-centered learning.

Table 9 shows an Observation Schedule on Teachers’ digital literacy skills and Competency Based Curriculum

Table 9: Observation Schedule on Teachers’ digital literacy skills and Competency Based Curriculum

Item	Rating (1-5) where Poor, 2-Fair, 3-Good, 4-Very Good, Excellent	Comment/ Observation
Teacher digital literacy skills		
1. Availability of computers in the school	• 2	● There are sufficient computers available for teachers and students
2. Have been trained to use ICT in CBC	• 5	● The teachers have received formal training in using ICT for CBC and training content relevant to current teaching needs
3. How often are the computers used for teaching	• 5	● computers are utilized in lessons daily
4. Alignment of technology with stated objectives	• 4	● The use of technology is aligned with CBC objectives
5. Effectiveness of ICT in teaching	• 5	● Students engage and participate actively during ICT-integrated lessons
6. How often do you use internet for searching educational content	• 2	● Digital resources (websites, online articles) utilized in lessons
7. Setting up ICT devices for learning	• 3	● Teachers independently set up ICT devices for use

Table 9 shows that the ratings of 5 were on Have been trained to use ICT in CBC, How often are the computers used for teaching and Effectiveness of ICT in teaching respectively while those with the ratings of 4 was Alignment of technology with stated objectives. This implies that teachers do prepare the schemes and lesson plan effectively and have a lot of confidence when teaching. The Head teachers were interviewed on Teachers’ digital literacy skills and Competency Based Curriculum coded as HA-HE. Their responses were as follows:

The lack of technological infrastructure, such as computers and internet connectivity limits teachers' ability to improve and use their digital literacy skills (School Head Teacher A, 2024).

There is need for tailored training focused on practical application of technology in CBC contexts, ensuring that teachers can leverage digital tools to enhance competency-based learning (School Head Teacher B, 2024).

Professional development programs for ongoing ICT training should be done frequently to build teachers' digital literacy skills (School Head Teacher C, 2024).

Teachers lacking ICT skills struggle with incorporating technology into lesson delivery, which affects the quality of CBC implementation since they rely heavily on traditional methods, limiting the interactive and collaborative aspects that CBC encourages (School Head Teacher D, 2024).

Teachers are able to integrate digital tools such as interactive learning platforms, e-assessments, and multimedia presentations into their lessons, which aligns with CBC's emphasis on student-centered, practical, and interactive learning. (School Head Teacher E, 2024).

From the above Head teachers' responses, we can imply that digital literacy plays an important role in the effective implementation of CBC, highlighting both the challenges and successes experienced within the schools.

The Curriculum Support Officers (CSO) were interviewed on Teachers' digital literacy skills and Competency Based Curriculum coded as CSO1-CSO2. Their responses were as follows:

CSO1:

"There is need for tailored training that addresses specific ICT needs for CBC implementation, such as using educational software, developing digital assessments, and utilizing online resources for lesson planning and should be ongoing and not limited to initial in-service sessions."

CSO2:

"Insufficient access to technology and internet connectivity can hinder teachers' ability to develop their digital literacy skills therefore there is need for increased investment in ICT infrastructure in schools, especially in rural or under-resourced areas, to facilitate effective CBC implementation"

From the Curriculum Support Officers (CSO) responses we can imply that the importance of ongoing, tailored training and improved access to technology are essential factors for enhancing teachers' digital literacy and ensuring successful implementation of the Competency-Based Curriculum."

The Quality Assurance and Standards Officers (QASO) were interviewed on Teachers' digital literacy skills and Competency Based Curriculum coded as QASO1-QASO2. Their responses were as follows:

QASO1:

"Teachers demonstrate a strong ability to integrate technology into their teaching practices, effectively utilizing digital tools to enhance learning although some teachers lack basic ICT skills, which negatively affects the implementation of CBC."

QASO2:

"Teachers who are proficient in using technology create more engaging and interactive learning environments, fostering students' critical thinking and collaboration skills, which are key components of CBC."

From the Quality Assurance and Standards Officers (QASO) responses we can imply that there is need to exhibit the importance of improving digital literacy among all teachers to ensure the effective implementation of the Competency-Based Curriculum.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that teachers' digital literacy skills has a great influence on implementation of Competency Based Curriculum

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i) The Teachers Service Commission ought to prioritize continuous professional development (CPD) programs focused on improving teachers' digital literacy skills on the use of AI tools, digital resources, and platforms that align with the objectives of the CBC
- ii) The Ministry of Education may allocate more resources for digital infrastructure in schools, particularly in junior schools, to support teachers in utilizing technology for teaching and learning.
- iii) KICD ought to develop and provide digital curriculum resources that align with the Competency-Based Curriculum with guidelines for the use of AI tools, e-learning platforms, and other digital technologies that teachers can integrate into their classrooms.
- iv) KEMI may provide leadership training for school administrators on the importance of supporting teachers' digital literacy development.
- v) School heads may be trained to create conducive environments for teachers to apply their digital literacy skills effectively in the CBC.

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